

COMPUTER SCIENCES

SOCIAL NETWORKING SERVICES

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Abstract

In the article, the services of Internet-media and social networks, this potential world trade, implementation of network monitoring, as well as production in the field of monitoring Internet-media resources, etc. investigated in studies. Nowadays, everyone can benefit from social networks. It can be network usage or otherwise oriented. Shab provides the abundance and availability of information, making the learning process more optimal and comfortable. Over the past 10 years, online social networks have become integral parts.

Keywords: Internet-media, network services, monitoring services, social network monitoring.

As a result of the possibilities of information and communication technologies, informatization acts as one of the main factors that stimulate the development of civilization. Wide use of these opportunities has led to the development of new approaches and trends in journalism. One of the main goals of the information policy of the state in our country is the application of ICT to mass media and its development according to world standards. Modern web technologies make it possible to more accurately and objectively determine the rating of electronic media, individual articles published in them, and the social composition of the readership. This is very important for the media to be able to establish their activities correctly. The application of such a system makes it possible to manage the quality of mass media.[1]

Media monitoring is the collection, systematic recording and analysis of published information. Media monitoring includes identifying and monitoring data sources, collecting and storing data, selecting the most relevant data through categorization and filtering, and analyzing the data collected. Media organizations conduct monitoring in order to effectively establish their activities in competition with other media organizations. Systematic collection of information allows obtaining accurate and reliable information on a given topic, evaluating the reputation of media organizations in the region or the country, and having an idea about the channels that transmit information. The evaluation of the obtained results enables more effective establishment of media resources activity and optimal decision-making. In modern times, monitoring of media resources does not only involve the analysis and search of information in traditional mass media, but also work with Internet resources, and at the same time forums with various topics that do not have the direct meaning of the term "media" but can have a significant impact on the formation of public opinion and serve as a source of information. also includes monitoring of blogs.[3]

Social media means creating virtual social communication and sharing information between people through Internet technologies. It transforms communication into an interactive dialogue using more accessible and web-based technologies. Social media tools include information sites broadcast over the Internet, social networks, blogs, micro blogs, instant communication programs, forums. Social networks are

a virtual form of our physical world. Currently, terrorist groups use social networks, e-mail, etc. they communicate with means. It is clear that among the types of information transmitted in such means of communication, texts are predominant. Therefore, in order to prevent possible terrorist acts and ensure the security of the state, the analysis of the texts circulating in the virtual environment, including social media, is of great importance.

Currently, Big Data analytics technologies (data mining, text mining, etc.) are used to discover examples, keywords and relevant information from texts.

When studying modern social network analysis, you can look at the experiments conducted by Stanley Milgram. After the attacks of September 11, 2001, social network experts began to give more priority to the use of network methodology in the fight against terrorism. Publications such as the Washington Post and the Dallas Morning News have written articles about network analysis. Many models (agent-based models, etc.) have been developed to help study the dynamic nature of social networks, and to study criminal or terrorist networks. [2]

Monitoring is a systematic process of collecting and analyzing data to ensure that a network (program, etc.) is progressing toward its goal and getting the right results. Social media monitoring helps to solve the issues mentioned below.

- to take into account the interests of the audience, people to accurately define their wishes and desires;
- create an interactive relationship with people;
- social media information that the audience needs spread through;
- to analyze the future activity of the institution.

During social media monitoring, information is initially monitored, texts are analyzed, and spam comments are determined. In the next steps, a more detailed analysis is carried out according to the various characteristics of the regions. Later, visualization and measures are taken against possible threats.[3]

Media monitoring is done through services offered by online media monitoring companies. These services are software that uses automated robots that automatically monitor the content of newspapers, magazines, TV channels, as well as free online news sources. The monitoring process is as follows: After the software has finished reading the text, it identifies the news text or

social media shares containing each customer's search term (keyword) and automatically presents relevant articles or social media "snippets" for each customer. Internet search systems or specialized mass media databases are usually used during monitoring. CyberAlert, the world's most well-known media monitoring company, monitors 50,000 online news sources in more than 75 languages in 189 countries every day. This company controls over 50 million social media blogs, 100,000 message boards, forums, complaint sites, over 200 video sharing sites and Twitter.[4]

It is known that social media means information sites, social networks, blogs, microblogs, forums, etc., broadcast over the Internet. includes. Many media organizations, in addition to monitoring news, also monitor social media and analyze information about them on social media. There are over 100 different social media monitoring and evaluation services. The most famous free blog monitoring service companies are Technorati, Blog Pulse, IceRocket, and Google Blogs. Technorati, one of the giant companies in the field of web services and software of the United States, claims that 75 thousand blogs with 1.2 million new posts containing opinions about the products and services of companies are created every day. Social media monitoring helps to solve the following issues: a) Listening to the audience, accurately determining people's wishes and desires; b) Creating an interactive relationship with people; c) Disseminate the necessary information through social media channels; d) To analyze the activity of the institution aiming at the future. Recently, journalists have been using their accounts on social networks to interact with people and learn about problems in society, and exchange ideas on topics of interest to them.[4]

Although the Internet-media is still in the formative stage in our country, there are enough online media resources related to Azerbaijan: blogs, forums, news portals. Currently, the commission on Internet media resources operates within the Press Council (MSC) to control Internet media resources in our country. This

commission reviews the complaints received by the Council about online mass media, monitors the trends in the current field, the innovations noticeable on the international scale, and also aims to help eliminate negative situations related to journalistic responsibility in the Internet media. "Media Tracking Center", "Net-trends" media monitoring company, "A-Vision" media and communication company, Azerbaijan Media Monitoring Institute, engaged in media monitoring and analysis in Azerbaijan, analyze media and social networks and build marketing strategies and tactics in accordance with current trends they offer a wide range of operative and professional services. The service areas of these companies include national media monitoring, foreign media monitoring, social media monitoring, news agency monitoring, media advertising monitoring.

The conducted research proves the importance of media monitoring today. As the media has a direct influence on public opinion and people's choices, one of the main goals of media professionals around the world today is to take advantage of the positive effects of the media and use them for the right purposes. For this purpose, mass media should conduct monitoring in order to establish their strategies correctly, and by making effective decisions, they can achieve an increase in the reputation of the site.

References

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